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ARCTIC OCEAN UNDER MELTING ICE (UNDER-ICE)

WP 2. DYNAMIC PROCESSES IN THE FRAM STRAIT MARGINAL ICE ZONE

by

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<p>SUMMARY: This report presents an overview of the work done in work package 2 of the project Arctic Ocean Under Melting Ice (UNDER-ICE), funded by the Research Council of Norway and ENGIE E&P Norge AS during 2014 and 2015.</p>	

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1 Introduction

This report presents an overview of the work done as part of UNDER-ICE, work package 2 (WP2), during 2014 and 2015. The tomographic system of the UNDER-ICE project (WP1) was deployed in September 2014, and the recovery is planned for summer 2016. The bulk of the new data generated during UNDER-ICE will be available only after successful recovery of the moored system in 2016. The activities in WP2 are therefore based mainly on data available from earlier work, i.e. prior to 2014. These previously existing data sources and associated processing are presented in Section 2. The research cruise in 2014 is briefly presented in Section 3. Preliminary results mainly based on legacy data (Section 2), are shown in Section 4. The results section, 4, is divided into two main themes, each of which represents a planned scientific publication. The first topic (4.1) is a case study of a crossing of the Arctic Front with ship and glider in September 2011. The second (4.2) is a study of mesoscale activity in the Fram Strait using the repeat sections from all glider deployments. Finally, in Section 5 I give an outlook describing the next steps, in particular publications that are planned or in preparation (5.1), and give some recommendations for future work (5.2) relating to issues covered in this report.

2 Legacy data sources

2.1 Mooring motion

2.1.1 Description

An acoustic tomography mooring system was deployed in the Fram Strait from August 2010 to September 2012 as part of the project ACOBAR - Acoustic technology for Observing the interior of the Arctic Ocean, 2008 - 2013. Knowing the three-dimensional position of the sound source and receivers with high precision at any time of measurement is crucial for the accuracy of acoustic thermometry. Therefore, a network of transponders were placed around each mooring, for the purpose of acoustically determining the position of the source and the receivers. The moorings deployed in 2010 and 2011 did not include instruments for directly measuring current velocity. The mooring position as recorded by the positioning array, however, shows the motion of the mooring as a result of being pushed by ocean currents. We want to explore the possibility of extracting information about the currents from the mooring displacement data.

2.1.2 Data return and quality

The positions of the moorings and the approximate (minimum) depth levels of the instruments are shown in table 1. The mooring array was designed and deployed with four moorings, but unfortunately one of them (C, at 79° 40'N, 0° 14'W) could not be recovered. Data is available only from moorings A, B, and D; we will only discuss these three and will refer to D as the northernmost mooring (ignoring C).

2.1.3 Analysis

Data from the transponder networks had been processed (by Florian Geyer) and the results saved as Matlab .mat files containing the displacements (in metres) in the x, y, and z directions for the source and receivers on each mooring. Further analysis of the mooring motion data were done in Matlab. Mooring designs were entered element by element into the Matlab package *Mooring Design and Dynamics* (Dewey, 1999), using the design sketches found in cruise reports and estimating unknown details.

2.1.4 Results and discussion

Mooring A, the easternmost mooring, at about $77^{\circ} 54'N$, $8^{\circ} 45'E$ (see table 1), was located at ca 1400 m water depth on the continental slope off Svalbard, i.e. in the West Spitsbergen Current regime. The current throughout the two deployment periods, 2010--2011 and 2011--2012, was consistently directed towards the north-northwest with little variation (see fig. 1a). Presumably, the current was aligned with topography (need to be compared with detailed bathymetry). The cumulative displacement was the largest at the westernmost mooring, B ($78^{\circ} 10'N$, $4^{\circ} 15'W$). This indicates that the currents there were persistent in direction, and probably also strong (although mooring design also plays a role in determining the magnitude of knock-down, as discussed below). On average the current at B was directed toward south-southeast, but with twist and turns indicating eddy motion (fig. 1b). The current at mooring D, the northernmost of the three recovered moorings, at about $78^{\circ} 54'N$, $2^{\circ} 20'E$, was more variable than at the other mooring sites. The overall current direction was mainly towards the west, but with significant deviations (fig. 1c).

Figure 1. Progressive vector plot of horizontal mooring displacement at a) mooring A, b) mooring B, and c) mooring D, over the whole period 2010--2012. The starting point (0,0) is marked by a red ring. Colours along the track indicate vertical displacement; zero is dark blue, and yellowish colours represent the strongest knock-down.

Velocities at various heights above seabed can be entered into MDD to test the effect of subjecting a mooring of a given design to a given velocity profile. An example result, of subjecting mooring A (approximate design) to a hypothetical current profile going from 50 cm s^{-1} at the surface to 0 cm s^{-1} at the bottom, can be seen in fig. 2. Mooring design is an important factor for the magnitude of mooring knockdown. Although "the drag of currents of order $\sim 1 \text{ kn}$ across the upper kilometre of a rig will cause even the stiffest moorings in deep water to cant over" (Pingree, 2002), there is large variation in mooring stiffness and drag depending on the buoyancy, size, shape, and positioning of the in-line elements.

Figure 2. Output from MDD: mooring A forced by hypothetical currents. The current profile is shown in green (u) and pink (v ; 0 in this case).

In order to make better estimates of the relationship between current velocity and mooring knockdown in the case of the ACOBAR acoustic moorings, it is important to know as many details as possible about what type of flotation was used, at what depth. MDD requires detailed input including all line, shackles etc. used. In the example (fig. 2), the horizontal displacement is less than 80 m although the input surface current was 50 cm s^{-1} . This suggests that in order to achieve horizontal displacements as large as actually measured at mooring A (see fig. 3), the input current velocities might have to be unrealistically high. For better mooring motion simulation, better information on all mooring elements needs to be entered, and, ideally, real velocity profiles from observations should be applied.

Figure 3. Horizontal versus vertical displacement of mooring A during the a) 2010-2011 and b) 2011-2012 deployment. S = Source, R = receiver. Corresponding figures for moorings B and D are found in Appendix.

Time series of vertical displacement show that there were relatively quiescent periods interspersed with periods of generally stronger knock-down (see for example mooring A, fig. 4). The strongest knock-down events occurred in late winter or early spring: in the beginning of February at mooring B, in March at A, and in April at D, possibly linked to seasonal variations in current strength. The largest vertical displacement was observed at mooring B, with a maximum of 345 m; maximum vertical displacement at moorings A and D were 198 and 277 m, respectively.

Figure 4. Time series of vertical displacement at mooring A, cf. fig. 3. Corresponding figures for moorings B and D are found in Appendix.

The most marked peak in the power density spectra of x, y, z displacements (fig. 5) was at the frequency of the semidiurnal tide (12.42 h). Note that the semidiurnal tidal frequency can hardly be distinguished from the inertial frequency at the latitudes of the moorings (12.23 hours at 78°N). The semidiurnal peak was the largest at all moorings, and moorings B and D also displayed a marked power spectral peak at the diurnal frequency, which was absent at

mooring A. The power spectra of displacement were overall of a "red noise" character, i.e. with the highest energy levels found at low frequencies, as is typical for oceanographic time series (e.g. current velocities).

Figure 5. Power spectral density of mooring motion at a) mooring A, b) mooring B, and c) mooring D. The dashed grey vertical line corresponds to a fortnightly frequency, the thin black line the semidiurnal frequency, and the dotted line (practically coincident with the semidiurnal) the inertial frequency, 12.23 hours.

2.2 Seagliders

2.2.1 Description

The Seaglider is an autonomous underwater vehicle that gets propulsion by changing its buoyancy (Eriksen *et al.*, 2001). Wings and a tail fin help convert vertical into forward motion so that the glider moves through the water in a sawtooth pattern. The glider measures temperature, conductivity and pressure along its path, and can be equipped with additional sensors for measuring other parameters. The displacement of a glider relative to its dead-reckoned path during a dive gives a measure of the depth-averaged current.

A total of nine Seaglider missions were completed in the Fram Strait in the years 2008--2013. Here, we will ignore the ninth glider mission, which followed a track from south to north in the Greenland Sea, and focus on the first eight missions that were flown generally in an east-west orientation between about 78° and 79°N. The plan of the missions was to cross the Fram Strait from about 9°E and as far west as ice conditions would allow (to about 3°W) along a zonal track parallel to and south of the mooring array at 78° 50'N.

2.2.2 Data return

Each of the five years, 2008 - 2012, there was a summer mission from July to September (see table 2). With the exception of the first two years, there was also an autumn mission with deployment in September and planned recovery in November. Unfortunately, because of different technical problems, none of the three gliders used in autumn missions were recovered. For details on glider deployment and recovery operations, see the cruise reports: Sagen *et al.*, 2010; Sagen, 2011; and Sagen *et al.*, 2012. Technical difficulties notwithstanding, all gliders flew for at least 1.5 - 2 months, and completed some 200 successful dives down to a maximum depth of about 1000 m (table 2). The gliders measured temperature, conductivity, pressure, dissolved oxygen and light transmission. The average dive-climb cycle took about 5.5 hours and covered a horizontal distance of about 4 km. The vertical resolution of the raw glider data depends on the glider's vertical velocity, which varies throughout each dive, and the sampling frequency (which can be set to different values for different parts of the dive). For the Fram Strait glider missions the (absolute)

difference in pressure between consecutive readings ranged between 0 and 10 dbar, with an average of 1.0 dbar.

Figure 6. Data coverage of all Seaglider missions 2008 - 2012 in space.

Figure 7. Time coverage of Seaglider missions.

2.2.3 Data processing and quality

The Seaglider transfers data via Iridium satellite to the base station on land. For each dive, a log file (.log) is created, containing a list of the Seaglider's parameters and their values for that dive, and GPS information from the period at the surface prior to the dive (see Seaglider Quality Control Manual (2012)).

Engineering (.eng) data files are also created for each dive. They contain data on the state and flight of the glider in engineering units, and also data from the sensors installed on the glider ("science" data). A file called `sg_calib_constants.m` containing calibration constants and other control parameter values is supplied by the user once for each deployment. After basic processing, the information from the log and engineering files - recorded data and any derived results - are written to a NetCDF (.nc) file. These were used for preliminary work, awaiting the complete post-processing procedure described below. For the preliminary glider data analysis, the uncorrected data were processed *ad hoc*. For some applications, the up-cast from one dive and the down-cast from the next dive were averaged in 5 dbar bins, thus creating "vertical profiles" assigned to the mean position and time of the two casts (Høydalsvik et al., 2013).

In order to ensure the best possible quality, glider data must undergo a multi-step procedure of processing and quality control. The format of the glider output and the mismatch in time

between the scientific and navigational systems of the glider contribute to making the task challenging (see e.g. poster by Beltran et al., 2015). Several groups are developing toolboxes for the purpose of glider data management/processing. For the work reported here, I used the Matlab toolbox developed by Bastien Queste and others at the University of East Anglia (UEA). The toolbox offers a large improvement compared to developing the processing from scratch, but it is still work in progress and its all routines are not yet fully functional. The main steps in the processing and quality-control procedure are:

1. Load calibration values, parse log- and eng-files, place all together in a Matlab structure
2. Initial checks to validate settings, data fields, and GPS data
3. Correct pressure and create time array (see *i* below)
4. *Create offset time and pressure array for each sensor (*ii*) [not currently implemented]
5. Regress flight model - first approximation (*iii*)
6. First rough pass of T - S data (*iv*)
7. Verify maximum volume and hydrodynamic parameters; calculate flight speed (*v*)
8. Clean pass of T - S data
9. Calculate vertical velocities, depth-averaged currents, and interpolated GPS positions (*vi*)
10. Process other sensor data, e.g. optode, transmissometer (*vii*)

Further explanation of some of the steps of the procedure can be found below. The UEA Seaglider data processing tools could not be applied to the data from Seaglider SG127 ("Agathe", used during summer missions), because it was running an older type of glider software with an older sensor naming convention. A possible work-around for the problem would be to replace sensor names in the header lines of .eng files from SG127 with names according to the current naming convention upon which the Matlab tools are based (Bastien Queste, pers. comm.).

- i. *Pressure correction:* The glider measures pressure, but converts this onboard using a linear factor of 0.685 m/psi, in order to report depth (m) in the eng-file. In this step, depth is back-calculated to pressure (psi) and then converted to dbar. Time is converted to Matlab format.
- ii. **Time and pressure offsets:* The glider collects data from the installed scientific instruments at some sampling rate set by the user. A time stamp is set at the beginning of each sampling cycle. The sensors are sampled serially, not simultaneously, so the readings from different sensors (although assigned to the same time stamp) are in fact offset in time. The practical lower limit of the sampling interval is 4 seconds, or possibly down to 2 seconds if only conductivity (C) and temperature (T) are sampled (Seaglider Pilot's Guide (2011)). As the glider moves through the water, the offset in time means different sensors sample at slightly different locations. Any resulting error will be larger when the glider travels through sharp gradients.
- iii. *Flight model:* The depth of the glider, and thus its vertical velocity relative to the sea surface, is known from the readings of the pressure sensor. The velocity of the glider relative to the water is not measured directly, but can be modelled. Glider flight is typically modelled as a balance between buoyancy and drag. Merckelbach et al. (2010) developed a dynamic model for planar glider flight which involves three calibration parameters: drag coefficient, hull compressibility, and glider volume. In this step of the data processing procedure, a first approximation of glide slope and speed is calculated from the vertical velocity derived from pressure, the measured pitch angle, and the hydrodynamic parameters of the glider.

- iv. *CT data:* The instrument installed on the glider to measure seawater conductivity and temperature - from which other properties such as salinity and density are derived - is a CTsail from SeaBird Electronics (SBE). Unlike the CTD configuration normally used on board ships, the CT-system on the glider is not pumped, in order to conserve battery power, and instead it is the glider's motion through the water that creates flow through the conductivity cell (see e.g. Perry et al., 2008). The temperature sensor has a relatively slow response time, which leads to a mismatch between the temperature and conductivity (and pressure) readings. The resulting error is larger in strong gradients, and would be even more problematic if it were not for the slow profiling speed of the glider (Bishop, 2008). The temperature sensor response time is constant, not dependent on flow speed or temperature (Queste, 2013), and can thus be corrected by applying a constant time offset.
Another source of error is the thermal mass or thermal inertia of the conductivity cell. The conductivity sensor response time is fast, but the measurement takes place inside a cell which has the capacity to store heat (Morison et al., 1994; Garau et al., 2011). Since conductivity depends strongly on temperature, the heat stored or released from the conductivity cell as it moves through a temperature gradient causes a significant bias in the measurements. The thermal inertia error varies with the flow speed through the cell, which is determined by the glider speed. The error appears as a systematic difference between dive and climb profiles (figure 8). The C-T corrections in the UEA glider processing toolbox include both the sensor response time offset and a correction for cell thermal mass based on the methodology proposed by Morison et al. (1994) and developed for application to gliders by Garau et al. (2011).
- v. *Flight speed:* A better approximation of glider flight is performed iteratively, using regression of parameters over many dives. Volume, buoyancy, flight slope and speed are all verified in this step.
- vi. *Depth-averaged current:* When under water the glider uses dead reckoning - based on the measured pressure (giving vertical motion), pitch, and heading - to estimate its position. The difference between the dead-reckoned position and the GPS fix the glider receives upon surfacing is the total effect of currents that have acted upon the glider throughout the dive cycle, and is known as the depth-averaged current. The UEA glider processing toolbox uses a travel estimate from the flight model as well as the distance determined from GPS coordinates to get the best possible estimate of current velocity. The glider's hypothetical trajectory without currents can also be estimated.
- vii. *Other sensors:* If calibration data for the Wetlabs optical sensor package (typically measuring fluorescence, transmissivity, and optical backscatter), these data are processed in this step. In terms of processing dissolved oxygen data, the UEA glider toolbox currently only includes a routine for processing data from Aanderaa oxygen optode 4330 (AA4330). Some of the gliders deployed in the Fram Strait had a different type of optode, Aanderaa's AA3830, which cannot be processed using the existing toolbox function. Seaglider SG127 ("Agathe") had yet another type of dissolved oxygen sensor, the SBE43.

Figure 8. Mean profile of uncorrected salinity versus pressure for each glider mission. Average of all down-casts in black, and of up-casts in red. (For mean temperature profiles, see Appendix.)

For results of the analysis of Seaglider data from the Fram Strait deployments, see section 6. Data specifically from the autumn 2011 mission are used in the case study of the front crossing (Sec. 6.1), and data from all the glider missions are included in the analysis of mesoscale features observed in the repeated zonal sections (Sec. 6.2).

2.3 Research cruises

2.3.1 Description

Research cruises as part of the ACOBAR project took place in 2010, 2011, and 2012 on board the RV Håkon Mosby and the KV Svalbard. During these research cruises the tomographic moorings were deployed, serviced, and recovered. Gliders were deployed and recovered. Other field experiments and observations were also conducted, addressing various topics such as passive acoustics, acoustic navigation/communication, sea ice measurements, and ice drift. Oceanographic measurements were made using the CTD system on board the RV Håkon Mosby, and during the research cruise in 2011 water samples to be analysed for nutrients and chlorophyll were also taken. On board the KV Svalbard, physical oceanography measurements were made using expendable instruments (XBT and XCTD). Data were also recorded by the shipboard ADCP and scientific echo-sounder on the RV Håkon Mosby. For more details on the cruises, I refer to the cruise reports that are available from the NERSC Polar and Acoustic Oceanography group upon request. Here I report only on the physical oceanography data from the research cruise on the RV Håkon Mosby in 2011 that have been analysed as part of UNDER-ICE WP11.

2.3.2 Data return and processing

A total of 28 CTD profiles were done in the eastern Fram Strait during the 2011 research cruise. Water samples were collected during 26 of the stations. The first 13 stations, n.o 944 - 956, started at the continental slope off Svalbard at 77° 54'N, 8° 45'E and followed a northwestward track to 78° 54'N, 2° 20'E (see fig. 9). The other transect, B (stations 958 - 971) was made from 79° 26'N, 1° 14'E and south-eastward back to the starting point (mooring A). Station 957 was not part of either transect: it was a shallow profile without water samples, done only to provide a sound speed profile.

A total of 309 nutrient samples (mostly from the upper 800 m) and 155 chlorophyll samples (upper 100 m) were collected. Samples were analysed for nitrite, nitrate, phosphate, silicate, salinity, chlorophyll-a, and phaeopigments at the Institute of Marine Research, Bergen.

The CTD package measured pressure, temperature, conductivity, dissolved oxygen, fluorescence, and optical transmissivity. Basic processing following standard routines was done on board using Seabird software; further processing and analysis was done using Matlab. I used 1 dbar resolution data from down-casts only.

Figure 9. Map showing CTD stations completed on the 2011 research cruise on the RV Håkon Mosby along transects A (squares) and B (triangles). Shading shows bathymetry with a contour interval of 500 m, see colour bar on the right. Glider tracks corresponding to the CTD sections are marked with black dots; each dot marks the mean position of one glider dive.

2.3.3 Results

A θ -S diagram for all CTD profiles during the 2011 research cruise with RV Håkon Mosby is shown in figure 10. The largest spread of temperatures and salinities were found in the upper 500 - 600 m, where temperatures ranged from -1.5°C to >6°C and salinities as low as 32 (PSU) were found in the parts of the survey most influenced by Polar Water. A larger volume (although small in θ - S space because of more homogeneous conditions) was taken up by waters characterized as Deep Water. Further results and analysis, focussing on transect B, are presented in section 6.1.

Figure 10. θ - S diagram for all 28 CTD stations of the 2011 HM cruise, whole range (a) and zoomed in on the deeper waters (b). Water masses labelled are: Atlantic Water (AW), Polar Water (PW), and Deep Water (DW). The deep waters are subdivided into Upper Polar Deep Water (UPDW), Norwegian Sea Deep Water, cold (NSDW_c), Canadian Basin Deep Water (CBDW), Greenland Sea Deep Water (GSDW; not observed) and Arctic Intermediate Water (AIW; not observed), cf. fig. 3 in Langehaug and Falck (2012); for water mass definitions, see their table 2.

3 Research cruises in 2014 and 2015

3.1 UNDER-ICE, KV Svalbard 2014

A research cruise was arranged on board the KV Svalbard in August--September 2014. During the cruise five acoustic moorings, accompanied by transponder networks, were deployed as part of the UNDER-ICE project; three oceanographic moorings were deployed for the NICE project; and some moorings were recovered on behalf of the Alfred Wegener Institute. Oceanographic sections were completed along paths between the acoustic moorings using XBTs and XCTDs.

A total of 40 XBTs were fired, 4 of which failed (several more gave questionable data and/or a short cast). Out of the 13 XCTDs that were fired, all except one completed successful casts. A temperature - salinity diagram based on all the available XCTD casts (XCTDs measure conductivity, so that salinity can be computed, while the XBTs give only temperature) is shown in figure 11, along with an overview of XCTD station positions.

On all western stations, very fresh and cold Polar Water was found in the upper layer (see fig. 11). There was a clear transition from the polar regime in the north-west into warm, saline Atlantic Water on the south-eastern part of the diagonal section. The middle station on this line fell on a mixing line between the Polar and Atlantic endpoints. Except for the westernmost stations, which were clearly in the Polar domain, the profiles on the northern

transect roughly along 80°N also showed a mixture of Polar and Atlantic properties. The warmest, most saline Atlantic Water was found in the south-eastern part of the study area and did not extend to the 80°N section. The warmest (up to 7°C) surface water was found at the south-easternmost station at about 9°E.

Figure 11. T-S diagram of all XCTD profiles during the UNDER-ICE research cruise on board KV Svalbard in August - September, 2014. Coloured by longitude from west (blue) to east (red); positions shown in inset. Black crosses in inset are XBT profiles.

3.2 FS2015, RV Lance 2015

The Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI) have annual research cruises to the Fram Strait to service moorings in the array along 78° 50'N that has been maintained since 1997 by NPI and the Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI) in co-operation. During the annual cruises, hydrographic sections are also completed across the Strait and in the surrounding areas. I participated in the 2015 cruise on board the RV Lance. Apart from the mooring work and the main zonal hydrographic section across the Fram Strait, further CTD/LADCP and water sampling was done along several smaller section on the East Greenland Shelf. In addition, sea ice observations were made en route as well as on ice floe stations. Data from the scientific echo sounder (Simrad EK60) were recorded for a pilot study of acoustically reflective thermohaline fine structure at water mass boundaries. In this report, I will only present some of the oceanographic observations relevant to UNDER-ICE, namely those from the zonal section just south of 79°N. I will only briefly mention the echo sounder data that are not yet processed and are not *per se* part of UNDER-ICE.

The echo sounder recorded raw data to file along the whole cruise track with only short breaks for technical reasons. The maximum ping range was adapted to fit the changing depths. Different settings in terms of pulse duration and ping rate were tested. We had planned to collect data from two frequency channels, but only the 18 kHz transceiver was operational. A total of 22 Gb of data from the 18 kHz channel were recorded during 18 days, covering a wide range of environments: from the Svalbard region in the east to the East Greenland shelf in the west, from shallow (ca 100 m) to deep (ca 2500 m) water.

The very cold and fresh waters of the East Greenland Current were present as a wide band above the shelf, while the waters in the central Fram Strait (between about 0° and 2°W) were more characteristic of the recirculation zone with its admixture of warm, saline Atlantic Waters (fig. 12). At the shelf edge, the presence of an eddy made isotherms and isohalines slope up and separated the easternmost part of the low-salinity wedge from the main body of the EGC.

Figure 12. Results from the first occupation of the west-east CTD section across the Fram Strait during the 2015 research cruise on board the RV Lance. a) Station positions; b) θ -S diagram; c) longitude vs depth plot of potential temperature; d) ditto for salinity. Adapted from original figure by P. Dodd.

Figure 13. Screenshot of ER60 echogram from 10 September, going from ca 1000 m (left side) to 290 m (right) water depth over the Svalbard shelf. The image captured one of the last CTD-casts of the cruise followed by an optics cast. The scattering layer likely consists of zooplankton. The wavelength of the 18 kHz signal is too long to target zooplankton individuals, but scattering can occur from thick patches of zooplankton or from larger animals like fish.

4 Preliminary results

4.1 Case study: Front crossing

During the research cruise with RV Håkon Mosby in August-September 2011, the Arctic Front in the Fram Strait was crossed with the ship and a glider following the same north-west to south-east track, transect B. (Transect A did not cross the front squarely, but cut along the edge of a frontal eddy or meander. Hereafter, 'transect' refers only to transect B.) We study the front at this time with particular focus on properties and processes important to marine life.

A marked boundary between cold surface waters generally in the north and west and warmer waters in the south and east is clearly visible in a satellite sea surface temperature (SST) image from the time of the observations (fig. 14). The north-western half of the CTD transect took place in what appears to be a cold meander protruding from the cold side of the front into the warmer waters, making the temperature gradient even stronger than in the surrounding regions. Along-track measurements of surface layer temperature (2 m depth) showed the sharpest increase, from less than 2°C to about 6°C over a short distance between stations 964 and 965 in the middle of the transect. The air temperature largely reflected the surface layer temperature, with colder air temperatures over the Polar Water domain and warmer air over the eastern part of the transect, although with more gradual changes.

Figure 14. Sea Surface Temperature (SST) from satellite. CTD stations shown as white crosses, with labels (A and B) at the northern end of each section.

Figure 15. Time series of air temperature and the temperature of sea water at 2 m (the depth of the water intake on the RV Håkon Mosby) along transect B, crossing the front. CTD stations are marked and labelled along the top.

The coldest upper waters, found in the near-surface layer at the north-western end of section B, were also the freshest. Temperatures as low as -1.5°C and salinities as low as 31.93 were found in the upper layer at stations 958 and 959. (The temperature and salinity minima did not coincide.) There was much small-scale variability in the cold and fresh upper waters on the north-western half of section, and a high level of interleaving of layers separated by sharp gradients (fig. 16). Temperature reversals were common in these waters. All the profiles on this side of the front had salinity minima in the upper 10 m, often of well below 33. On the south-eastern side of the front, maximum temperatures ($>6^{\circ}\text{C}$) were found in the ca 50 m thick surface mixed layer. In the surface mixed layer, salinities were lower than below,

although still significantly higher than on the polar side of the front. The highest salinities on the Atlantic side of the front were found in the upper 200 m, with maxima just below the base of the surface mixed layer, and from there decreased downward to minima (along with minimum temperatures) at depth.

Figure 16. Temperature section from CTD profiles taken during the 2011 research cruise on board RV Håkon Mosby. Station locations are marked by black triangles along the top edge of the section. Isotherms as black lines at 1°C intervals. On the horizontal axis is distance from the first - north-westernmost - station on section B (cf. fig. 14; station numbers in fig. 15).

The upper waters on the polar side of the front contained lower concentrations of nitrite, nitrate, and phosphate than those on the Atlantic side, but were higher in silicate (fig. 17). Chlorophyll-a concentrations (not shown) were lower in the surface layer and showed a subsurface chlorophyll maximum at 40 - 75 m depth. Chlorophyll concentrations were generally lower on the Atlantic side of the front, and here they were highest in the surface layer, and decreased below about 50 m.

Figure 17. Nutrient profiles from transect B, colours show location from north-west (blue) to south-east (red).

Turner angles, which provide a measure of the stability of a water column to double-diffusive convection, were computed for all the profiles on the CTD transect. In profiles on the polar side of the front, conditions were mostly conducive to double-diffusive instability in the upper few hundred metres (fig. 18a). Below that, the portion of the water column likely to favour salt fingering increased down to about 700 m depth. On the south-eastern (or Atlantic) side of the front, in contrast, the upper layer was not conducive to double-diffusion. Instead salt-

fingering conditions prevailed except for an often mostly stably stratified layer in the upper 100 m (fig. 18b).

Figure 18. Turner angles for the north-western (a) and south-eastern (b) end stations of CTD transect B. Shown by the horizontal bars is the percentage of (1 dbar resolution) data points in each 50 dbar pressure bin that are characterized as gravitationally unstable ("unstable"), double-diffusively unstable ("DD"), salt fingering unstable ("SF"), or double stable ("stable").

4.2 Repeat sections: mesoscale eddies

Average temperature profiles measured during all five summer missions 2008--2012 for the areas east and west of 5°E are shown in figure 19. The longitude 5°E corresponds to the transition between the West Spitsbergen Current (WSC) and the recirculation zone as it appears in long-term mooring records (Beszczynska-Möller et al., 2012), as well as in the multi-year glider survey data (e.g. figure 20). Mean (and median) temperatures for the upper 500 m on each mission, averaged into 1° longitude bins, showed large interannual variation particularly in the western region (fig. 21); however, the east-west transition often with strongest gradients in the region between 4 and 6°E appeared to be consistent. The eastern and western regions are not equal in size - the measurements extended westward to beyond the 0° meridian, but eastward only to about 9°E - and the coverage in different parts of the study area varied from mission to mission. Still, the overall pattern of the mean temperature profiles (fig. 19) is representative of the WSC and the recirculation domains, respectively. The temperature down to about 700 m depth was higher in the eastern than the western area. Below about 800 m, the mean temperature in the west was somewhat higher. The variability was higher in the western region and at all depths, the eastern mean profile fell within the ± 1 standard deviation envelope of the western mean profile (figure 19). This is the result of the recirculation in the zone west of 5°E of the warm Atlantic Water that dominates the eastern zone. Thus, in the WSC, there is 'only' warm water with relatively little spread; in contrast, further west, where the average temperature is lower due to the presence of colder Polar Water, there is still commonly an influence of Atlantic Water.

Figure 19. Mean temperature profiles from all summer glider missions east (red) and west (blue) of 5°E. The shaded area shows ± 1 standard deviation. Note the different horizontal and vertical scales above and below 200 m (top and bottom panel). Uncorrected data.

Figure 20. Mean temperature (bold lines) for the upper 500 m in 1° longitude bins from each summer glider mission. Thin lines are the median values for each 1° longitude bin.

Figure 21. Average current vectors from the eight Seaglider missions (colours as in fig. 6 and 7). Depth-averaged current velocities - inferred from glider drift - for each mission have been averaged over 1° longitude bins. Dives shallower than 400 m and bins with less than 15 dives are excluded. Uncorrected data.

In most of the quasi-zonal sections, isotherms (or isopycnals, that mirror the isotherms) show a number of up- or downward bulges with lengths of about 20 - 45 km (see fig. 22 and fig. 23). Often, the presence of several such features on a section give the isotherms an undulating appearance.

Figure 22. Temperature contours plotted against longitude, from a repeated quasi-zonal transect with glider MK501 in autumn 2010. The bottom panel indicates the distance of the glider track from the $78^\circ 50' N$ line (the latitude of the AWI/NPI mooring array); the different colours refer to panels 1 - 4 as

shown in the legend on the right. Dates in green show start and end dates of each transect, and arrows show direction of travel. Uncorrected data. Corresponding figures for the summer glider missions the same year and the following year are found in Appendix.

Because of the glider's slow speed, high-frequency variability (caused by e.g. internal waves) becomes projected upon the spatial structure (Rudnick and Cole, 2011). The gliders thus do not provide a synoptic view, and care must be taken in interpreting glider sections. In the repeat sections from the Fram Strait, however, the same (or similar) mesoscale features often appear in consecutive glider transects, indicating that the decorrelation time of these features may be longer than the repeat interval. By selecting features - for example simply defined as minima or maxima in the height of a given isopycnal - automatically throughout a whole glider mission, statistics can be collected on the characteristic length scales and amplitudes of these features. For the example shown in fig. 23, isopycnal height is plotted versus distance from the starting point of the track, regardless of the orientation of the trajectory or the direction travelled at any time. For this treatment to be meaningful one must assume that the mesoscale field is isotropic (and quasi-static on the time scale of the repeat interval).

Figure 23. Temperature (top) and potential density anomaly σ_θ (bottom) along several repeated transects with glider MK501 in autumn 2010. Black contour lines are the 0 and 4°C isotherms and the $\sigma_\theta = 28.0$ [kg m⁻³] isopycnal, respectively. The red line is the smoothed $\sigma_\theta = 28.0$ isopycnal. Vertical black lines mark turns at eastern or western end points. The second through fifth segment correspond to the transects shown in figure 22. Blue and red filled circles are automatically selected minima and maxima, respectively; black, open circles are extrema too close to transect end points. Only transects with at least five dives are included. Uncorrected data; up-and down-casts averaged to 5 dbar vertical resolution.

5 Outlook

5.1 Planned future activities and dissemination

Two scientific publications are planned based on the work done in UNDER-ICE WP2, following the themes outlined in sections 6.1 and 6.2 of this report.

5.2 Recommendations

In order to complete the analysis of the ACOBAR glider data, the following steps should be considered:

1. Rewrite header lines in order to be able to process SG127 data with UEA toolbox.
2. Write a function for the Aanderaa optodes used on 'our' gliders - there is no support for this model in the existing toolbox.
3. (optional, depending on the success with steps 1 and 2) Try out the SOCIB data processing toolbox as an alternative to the UEA toolbox.

Regarding mooring motion, the inclusion of current meters or profilers in addition to acoustic instrumentation on moorings will make it more meaningful to analyse mooring motion data as measured by transponders. Very detailed mooring design charts (not only the planned, but final) and as much information as possible about all the components of the mooring (weight, estimated drag if known, etc.) and information about the current field would make it possible to model the mooring motion using for example MDD software.

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Tables

Table 1. Table of mooring position data. Mooring positions are surveyed positions. src = source; hph = hydrophone. Instrument depths are minimum determined depths rounded off to the nearest whole metre.

Mooring	Deployment Recovery	Latitude Longitude	Instrument	Depth (m)	Record length (h)
A (I)	2010-08-02 2011-09-10	77°53.9912'N 08°44.8132'E	src	391	9261
			hph	357	9261
			hph	366	9261
			hph	375	9261
			hph	384	9261
A (II)	2011-09-23 2012-09-10	77°54.1173'N 08°44.4718'E	src	377	8445
			hph	343	8445
			hph	352	8445
			hph	361	8445
			hph	370	8445
B	2010-09-07 2012-09-05	78°09.6527'N 04°14.5812'W	src	461	17383
			hph	427	17383
			hph	436	17383
			hph	445	17383
			hph	454	17383
D (I)	2010-08-04 2011-09-11	78°53.7734'N 02°20.7386'E	src (a)	191	8792
			hph	198	8792
			hph	294	8792
			hph	390	8792
			hph	486	8792
			src (b)	880	8768
			hph	584	8768
			hph	680	8768
			hph	776	8768
			hph	872	8768
			D (II)	2011-09-24 2012-09-02	78°53.7063'N 02°19.6998'E
hph	234	8244			
hph	243	8244			
hph	252	8244			
hph	261	8244			
src (b)	954	8218			
hph	921	8218			
hph	930	8218			
hph	939	8218			
hph	948	8218			

Table 2. Table of glider missions. The season of deployment is labelled summer (S) or autumn (A). The table also shows which ship the glider was deployed and recovered from: the German RV Polarstern or the Norwegian coastguard icebreaker KV Svalbard (KV Sval.). Some gliders could unfortunately not be recovered (marked as “not rec.” in table).

Glider	Year Season	Mission start	Mission end	Success -ful dives	1000 m dives	Distance (km)	Deploy-ment	Recovery
SG127	2008 S	19 Jul	17 Sep	391	284	1391	Polarstern	KV Sval.
SG127	2009 S	4 Jul	17 Sep	372	275	1353	Polarstern	KV Sval.
SG127	2010 S	8 Jul	16 Sep	290	211	1016	Polarstern	KV Sval.
MK501	2010 A	17 Sep	28 Nov	277	224	1215	KV Sval.	Not rec.
SG127	2011 S	9 Jul	25 Sep	350	270	1284	Polarstern	KV Sval.
MK544	2011 A	24 Sep	15 Nov	198	178	831	KV Sval.	Not rec.
SG127	2012 S	14 Jul	7 Sep	212	156	908	Polarstern	KV Sval.
MK557	2012 A	9 Sep	25 Oct	197	163	861	KV Sval.	Not rec.

Appendix

Figure 24. Horizontal versus vertical displacement of mooring B during the whole deployment, 2010 - 2012. S = source, R = receiver.

Figure 25. Horizontal versus vertical displacement of mooring D during the a) 2010-2011 and b) 2011-2012 deployment. S = Source, R = receiver. Note that the design of mooring D was different to A and B in that it included two acoustic sources, one deep and one shallow, and two sets of receivers. The receiver configuration was changed between the first and the second deployment.

Figure 26. Mean profile of uncorrected temperature versus pressure for each glider mission. Mean of all down-casts in black, and of up-casts in red.

Figure 27. Temperature on repeated quasi-zonal section with glider SG127, summer 2010. Compare with figure 22. Uncorrected data.

Figure 28. As figure 27 but for summer 2011.